

An Analysis of Pepper (*Piper Nigrum*) Value Chains in Cambodia

Mr. Pisith SOK^{1*}

¹ M.S in Agri-business at Adelaide University, South Australia (SA). Deputy Director, Planning and Cooperation Department, Ministry of Labour and Vocational Training (MLVT), Royal Government of Cambodia (RGC)

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*Corresponding Author:
Mr. Pisith SOK,
psok24@gmail.com

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There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

Pepper is one of Cambodia's main crop exports. It has been significant growth of production in hectares (ha) and metric tons (MT) and got GI status from EU markets but markets access and value adding of the produce remain a constraint for small growers, as Cambodian pepper heavily relies on Vietnam and Thailand markets particularly Tboung Khmum (TK) pepper. On the other hand, local processors still struggle with modern machineries to process pepper into other forms (ground pepper, oil, oleoresin or medicine) and high competition with Vietnamese collectors for buying peppercorns. By using SWOT analysis, quantitative and qualitative statistics, this study explores the dynamic market opportunities for pepper value chains (PVC) development in Cambodia to maximize value chains (VC) actors' benefits and enabling business environment for investors. The study reveals that European (EU) markets, Japan, Korea, Taiwan, and the U.S are potential markets for Cambodian pepper exporting. Kampot (KP) pepper is identified as the taste of heritage and gets geographical indicator (GI) status from EU countries. Furthermore, contract farming (FC), (GI), and organic status are important factors for Cambodian pepper to target high value markets (premium price). By analysing SWOT tool shows that the strengths and opportunities are outweigh its weaknesses and threats particularly it is potential for investments and foreign direct investments (FDIs). The study found that challenges in the PVC such as limited planted areas (many small growers), shortage of processing techniques, lack of understanding market requirements, informal export to neighbouring countries (VN, TH), high interest rate of loans, and counterfeit on the name of Kampot pepper. To deal with these constraints, some solutions need to be addressed include expanding planted areas, improve productivity (KP pepper), enhance pepper quality (TK pepper), reduce dependency on Vietnam (grey market), more focus on end-user exporting markets, CF and organic status, strictly control licenses (GI & Organic), technology upgrading, diversify peppers, improve delivery system, and build brand equity. In addition, this research also found that peppers in

Cambodia are potential for export oriented, investments, and reduce poverty. Finally, VC analysis tool plays a crucial role to identify all the factors and actors of the pepper industry in the country.

Pepper is identified as the king of spices and one among the cash crop agricultural commodities of trade. It is valued as an ingredient for food cooking and as a spice. Cambodia is one of the largest pepper producers in South East Asia (SEA). Pepper is a climbing vine grown for its berries extensively used as spice and medicine. Pepper is considered the oldest agricultural commodity that is traded worldwide.

Keywords: Pepper, Value chains, Geographical Indication (GI), Contract farming (CF), premium price, SWOT, pepper corns, Organic, Value chains actors, spices.

Introduction

Pepper is one of the cash crops in the tropic area. It is also known as the king of spices. Peppercorn is planted in moist, hot climate and with the height of 457 metre above sea level with the rainfall of around 2.54 metre. It is well grown in fertile, flat or slightly sloping land which is rich in humus, good drainage, and light shade (IPC 2018). Pepper was one of the oldest commodities, which was brought to Asian in the 16th century (IPC 2018). There are four main types of pepper have been traded include green, black pepper, red, and white peppers. Green pepper is unripe fruit of the peppercorn. It has been harvested while it still young from the plant. It has a fresh citrus flavour and less spicy than the dried varieties. Black pepper is harvested when the berries turn from green to yellow, then they take it to dry to evaporate the water out. It has a deeper, stronger and vaguely floral flavour with hints of flowers, eucalyptus and mint. It can range from mildly sweet to intensely spicy. Red pepper is the dried product of fully ripe berries. It can be presented in full berries. Its taste is sweeter and less spicy than the black variety, but its flavour is more rounded. It has a powerful fruity aroma. White pepper is produced from red or ripe berries and the outer skin of the fruit is removed after the process of soaking, this process provides the product with a different taste of fresh grass and lime (Anna 2014). However, Black pepper is used in almost all forms of spice food with exception of baked goods (Yogesh M.S, Dr. S. Mokshapathy 2013). People use it in sauces, gravies, processed meats, steak, poultry, snack foods and so on (Naveen Kumar 2013). The global production of pepper rose dramatically from 2013 to 2017 with the amount of 379,300 tons to 501,495 tons by the volume of 12% annually (IPC 2018). Vietnam is a key player for growing in production by taking most pepper producers. However, other countries also increased significantly during this period namely India, Brazil, Indonesia, Malaysia, Sri Lanka, China and Cambodia (IPC 2018). Based on pepper sector profile in 2010 by Value Chain Unit of the Ministry of Commerce (MoC) of Cambodia shows that the total pepper production rose from 60 tons to 861 tons in 2000 and 2010 respectively. In 2000, there were two provinces producing pepper: Kampot and Mondulkiri. A decade later (2010), the production has expanded to other provinces but only two main provinces are the key pepper producer namely Tboung Khmum and Kampot. See fig. 1 and 2

Figure 1. Map of Cambodia in South East

Figure 1. Map of two target provinces of pepper producer

Furthermore, Cambodia is rapidly increasing its position in the global market in term of production and productivity. The production was 1,000 tons in 2011 to 21,000 tons in 2017 with the annual grow of 31%. The productivity was 4.5 to 7.2 tons per hectare. The average new planting was 40% from 2011-2017. Cambodian production is becoming more significant and important for global price dynamics (NEDSPICE 2017).

Cambodia has a centuries-long of planting pepper which started in the 13th century of Khmer Empire Angkor(Edgar 2016). The pepper production had been recorded formally in the 1960s after the French colonized the country for 90 years. During that time, most of the pepper produce grew in Kampot province, which was world reknown as “Kampot pepper”.

The study focuses on two provinces, Tboung Khmum and Kampot since they are the main producer of peppers in the country. Here are the objectives of the research study:

- 1) To understand and analyse the value chain of pepper in Cambodia particularly Tboung Khmum and Kampot provinces by doing value chain (VC) map of the structure of the industry.
- 2) To diagnose the current state of the industry to describe how the industry is structured, the number and type of actors, production, export, the current market prices, and flow of information.
- 3) To examine the present position, roles, relationship and different actors in value chain by identifying their challenges and opportunities.
- 4) To identify the enabling environment for businesses by using SWOT analysis.
- 5) To explore the solutions in response to challenges and provide recommendations.

Materials and methods

This study is a desk research project by exploring the key actors of value chain and potential market opportunities to promote the pepper value chain in Cambodia, using SWOT analysis and descriptive statistics methods. Desk research is a secondary research method that involves the summary and synthesis of existing studies, relevant journal articles, documents, and other reports. This method has been implemented in a study of the elements of green supply chain management, to suggest how companies can incorporate green supply chain tools in their value chain (Amemba et al. 2013). To conduct the significant finding of extent research, this research includes a study review of academic journal publications and other articles related to pepper production, markets, and prices. Meanwhile, in responding to RQ1 and RQ2, statistics data from International Pepper Community (IPC), Nedspices research, CIRAD's studies, UN-Comtrade statistic, ITC statistic, the Ministry of Commerce (MoC) and other data from official institutions are analysed for determining the types of actors in value chain, production, market prices, export volume (tonnes), export value (USD), and flow of information for the pepper industry.

In responding to RQ3 & RQ4, the key challenges and opportunities to pepper value chain (PVC) actors and business environment in Cambodia, this study uses SWOT to analyse them. This analytical tool explores internal and external environments to give systematic support for a decision, and to adapt fix strategy derived from the analysis of these factors. Qualitative data extracted from the literature review, are synchronized to formulate the SWOT analysis.

To response to RQ5, qualitative information is extracted to explore solutions for the chain actors in the PVC.

Finally, a synthesis of the evidence and finding from RQ1, RQ2, RQ3, RQ4, and RQ5 is then used to offer policy recommendations that aim to add value to pepper production in order to improve the performance of pepper exporting in Cambodia.

Results and discussion

World pepper prices and production

Based on observation, it has been seen that the global pepper farmers are now challenging with the low price of pepper in the last few years. However, the production of pepper is still high among the main producer countries. The main reason of decreasing price is significant increase of supply in the last few years particularly in Viet Nam, Brazil, Cambodia & Indonesia. Here is the world pepper production. See the table1

Table 1. The world production of pepper in metric ton (MT) from 2013-2018

Country	2013(MT)	2014(MT)	2015(MT)	2016(MT)	2017(MT)	2018(MT) est.
Vietnam	122,000	148,760	122,000	170,000	200,000	200,000
Indonesia	63,500	52,000	80,000	75,000	75,000	80,000
Brazil	34,000	39,000	44,000	45,000	60,000	57,020
India	65,000	37,000	70,000	48,500	57,000	65,000
China	28,000	28,000	29,000	29,000	29,000	29,500
Sri Lanka	28,000	14,139	28,177	18,500	25,995	18,150
Malaysia	19,000	20,500	22,500	23,000	23,500	24,000
Cambodia	6,000	7,500	9,845	11,819	20,054	20,000
Thailand	6,000	6,000	5,500	6,000	5,000	5,000
Madagascar	4,000	4,000	4,000	4,000	4,000	4,000
Other	3800	2,500	1,155	681	1,946	1,000
Total	379,300	359,399	416,177	431,500	501,495	503,670

Source: IPC's Statistics

After increasing price during a decade (2006-2015), the prices of pepper start going down. In New York spot price of black pepper decreased from USD 11,300 in mid-2015 to USD 2,200 per MT in 2016 while the white pepper fell from USD 16,500 per MT in 2015 to USD 3,860 in early 2016. Less than a few years after the peak, the price has dropped significantly more than 50% to the level of USD 3,640 per MT for black and USD 6,065 per MT for white pepper which are recorded at the end of June 2018. As mention above, the main reason of the decrease price is high increasing of supply in pepper markets. See the pepper price at New York in the figure 3.

Figure 1. Pepper prices at New York city from 2004- June 2018 (15 years) in USD/MT

Source: IPC's monthly market review on June-2018

Cambodia's pepper price and production

The pepper price in Cambodia is not different from the world. It jumped up in 2015 and 2016 with USD15 per kilogram and then it went down dramatically to USD10 per kilogram in 2017 and mid-2018. See the prices in the figure 3.

Figure 2. The prices of Kampot black-pepper from 2013 to Sep 2018 in USD/Kg

Source: MoC and (Lak 2018)

For the planted areas, Cambodia increased significantly from 2,279 ha in 2013 to 6,678 ha in 2017. It was increased 3 times just only 5 years period. It is similarly for production, it rose from 6,000 MT in 2013 to

20,054 MT in 2017. It means that Cambodia's production grew around 3 times compared to five years ago. See the figure 4.

Figure 3. Cambodian pepper planted areas and production from 2013 to 2017.

Source: MAFF 2017

For productivity, Cambodia is the third highest productivity of pepper in the globe after Tajikistan and Costa Rica with the yield of 6,462 kilograms per hectare. See the figure 5.

Figure 4. The top 10 countries of high productivity pepper in the globe by Kg/ha

Source: FAO-STAT

Cambodia's export of pepper

Cambodia's exports quantity of pepper grew significantly in the last few years with the amount of 665 MT in 2015 to 3,131 MT in 2017. See the figure 6.

Figure 6. Export quantity of pepper from Cambodia to the world in MT

Source: MAFF 2017 and IPC-MR Feb 2018

In addition, the trend is similar for the value (USD) of pepper export. It jumped from 1,595,000 USD in 2015 to 11,222,000 USD in 2017 based on the Ministry of Commerce (MoC) of Cambodia and the UN-Comtrade Statistics data. See the figure 7.

Figure 7. Export value in thousand USD of pepper from Cambodia to the world.

Source: UN-Comtrade Statistics and MoC

For the export partners, Cambodia has around 20 importers in the world. However, there are five main importers of Cambodian pepper namely Vietnam, Taipei-Chinese, France, Germany and USA with the value

of 1.526, 0.781, 0.524, 0.424, and 0.108 million USD respectively in 2016. Table 2. The main importer countries of Cambodian pepper from 2012-2016 in thousands USD.

Importers	2012 (1,000\$)	2013 (1,000\$)	2014 (1,000\$)	2015 (1,000\$)	2016 (1,000\$)
Viet Nam	457	0	0	381	1526
Taipei-Chinese	48	138	270	315	781
France	65	76	89	629	524
Germany	8	6	111	24	424
USA	2	0	0	0	108
UAE	0	0	0	0	85
Switzerland	3	3	17	29	40
Canada	0	5	0	0	25
Malaysia	0	0	0	0	12
Denmark	0	0	0	0	11
UK	0	0	0	0	11
Japan	1	0	0	42	5
Singapore	224	3968	6845	7	5
Turkey	0	0	0	0	3
India	0	0	0	0	1
Area Nes	0	9	0	0	0
Australia	4	3	5	9	0
Austria	4	0	0	0	0
Belgium	3	0	0	0	0
Korea	18	0	0	154	0
Netherlands	0	0	142	0	0
New Zealand	0	0	2	5	0
Norway	10	0	0	0	0
World	846	4208	7481	1595	3564

Source: UN-Comtrade Statistics

It has been seen that Vietnam is a main importer of Cambodian pepper exports. It took around 45% of Cambodia’s total exports (not include informal export). The figure 9 below is more detail about Cambodian pepper exporting to Viet Nam from 2012 to 2017 in quantity (MT) and value in thousands USD (KUSD).

Figure 8. Cambodian pepper exported to Vietnam in quantity (MT) and Value (KUSD)
 Source: IPC-PSY 2016 and IPC-MR Feb 2018

Value chain actors and mapping

Pepper is one of the cash crops for farmers in Cambodia. There are three main provinces namely Tbuong Khmum, Ratanakiri, and Kmapot provinces, which are key players of producing pepper in the country. Pepper value chain is necessary for local and international markets, but it has a few players who are operating in the big scale. Here are value chain actors for Cambodian pepper: input suppliers, pepper growers, collectors or intermediaries, associations and cooperatives, processors, and exporting companies. See the pepper value chain (PVC) map below:

Figure 9. Cambodian pepper value chain (PVC) map adapted from CIRD (PRAK 2015)

Input suppliers: materials and equipment including wooden poles, coconut leaves, and seeds (stems) are found in the local areas while plastics net, fertilizers, pesticides, hormones, irrigated tubes and valves, and other tools are supplied by farmer cooperatives & associations, and Vietnamese & Thai suppliers. Many Agri-companies has imported and sold widely fertilizers, insecticides, herbicides, and hormones in many local markets where the growers can access easily.

Pepper growers: Many of pepper growers involved in planting, irrigating, harvesting, and post-harvesting activities including water the plant, apply fertilizers and chemicals, harvest pepper berries, and dry berries by using sun-dry and solar-dry. Most of the growers sell their peppercorn after harvesting since they need money immediately to pay for their operation costs. Growers in Tboung Khmum and Ratanakiri provinces got market price information only from Vietnamese and Khmer local-collectors while Kampot pepper have their association (KAMPACO: Kampot Pepper Agricultural Cooperative) to inform the market price, agricultural inputs, and techniques. Moreover, Kampot pepper growers have contract farming (CF) with exporter companies (seven companies). Furthermore, Pepper growers in Tboung Khmum and Ratanakiri provinces have been sold their peppercorn at the farm gate while Kampot pepper growers have their own cooperatives, associations and exporter companies to buy directly.

Collectors or intermediaries: All collector or intermediaries do not crushing peppercorn to become ground pepper and not transform peppercorn into red and white peppers (Sim & Heng 2015).

For Tboung Khmum pepper, most of pepper collectors and middlemen in the province come from Vietnam. Many Vietnamese collectors normally come to buy peppercorns at the farm gate. Each Vietnamese collector bought between 200kg and 300 kg a day by using motorbikes to transport to Vietnam. There are also have Cambodian collectors to buy peppercorn from growers in Tboung Khmum and other provinces to sell in Phnom Penh city. Some collectors sold it to Thailand through Poipet border. Both Vietnamese and Cambodian collectors pay cashes to pepper growers at the farm gate (Sim & Heng 2015).

For Kampot pepper, the collector is cooperative and private companies. KAMPACO plays an important role to collect the pepper from members to sell as a group to traders or private companies. The cooperative (KAMPACO-Kampot Pepper Agricultural Cooperative) has member more than 241 members who make quality pepper for export to developed countries like the U.S, France, Germany, Switzerland, Japan, and Singapore. 50% of Kampot pepper production sold to seven companies under written contract (Farming Contract) (Thorng & Chao 2016).

Processors: Most of traders or local processors do crushing/grinding peppercorn to become ground pepper and transform peppercorn into white or red pepper. There are a few pepper processors in Phnom Penh capital including Two Dragons, Tiger Head, and so on. They buy peppercorns from collectors/intermediaries then convert into white, red, and ground peppers. The processor sells their products to retailers in Phnom Penh city particularly in conventional markets namely: Psa Oreussey, Psa Deum Kor, Psa Chbar Ampov, Psa Olympic, Psa Toul Tumpoung, Psa Kandal, and Psa Thom Thmey. Moreover, exporter companies are also doing processing pepper (Kong SIM 2015).

Associations and Cooperatives: If comparing between Tboung Khmum pepper and Kampot pepper, it reveals that Kampot pepper get more advantage than their counter part. Kampot pepper has both association and cooperatives to help growers in term of market prices and production techniques. For example, Kampot Pepper Agricultural Cooperative (KAMPACO) was established by Kampot pepper growers on Feb, 2009. The aims of this cooperative are to help pepper growers in doing their pepper business and to serve as collective structure to represent them in other negotiations. It plays a crucial role in determining price with partner companies or traders, collecting, and selling produces of all members. Moreover, it also shares information and experiences including growing techniques and market situation. Another supporting agency for Kampot pepper is Kampot Pepper Promotion Association (KPPA) which is working closely with 17 private companies to deliver Kampot pepper for domestic consumption and exporting overseas (Thorng & Chao 2016). Tboung Khmum pepper is also have a cooperative (Da-Memot Cooperative) but it is not function well.

Exporter companies: There are both local and international companies that registered at the Ministry of Commerce to export pepper from Cambodia to overseas. Olam Company is the third largest pepper exporter in the globe that has been exported Cambodian pepper since 2011 to present. There are also several local companies to export pepper to international markets such as, Farmlink Company, SELA PEPPER Company,

Long Best Development Company, Tang Huy Pheng Company, Khy Thay Corporation, Angkor Green Company, and so on (Sim & Heng 2015; Thorng & Chao 2016). Those companies export organic, GI and ordinary peppers to international markets.

Farmlink Company was established in 2006 in Kampot province. Farmlink core is to build the link between the growers and international buyers and purveyors. The company is a vital link in the Kampot Pepper supply chain. The company collects and processes the raw produce from growers to export. The company try to ensure the highest standards of cleaning, sort grading, and packing process in order to guarantee that the products not only attain but also surpass international food safety standards required for overseas markets. The company focuses on organic and GI pepper produce (Farmlink 2018) .

SELA PEPPER Company was created in 2014 in Memot district of Tboung Khmum province. The company has experiences in processing black pepper for world markets. The company set up factory and equipment to process and clean Memot pepper for exporting. It has capacity to clean and sort peppercorn around 1.5 MT per hour. The company aims to achieve the high demands of its customers and integrate Cambodian black pepper industry in the world market (SELAPEPPER 2018).

Market prices of pepper

The current pepper price (Sep 2018) is not change much compared to last year. The price of Kampot pepper is around USD10 (1USD=4,000 Cambodian Riels (CR) per kilogram while the price of ordinary pepper (Tboung Khmum and other provinces) is around USD 6 per kilogram. See the current price in the table 3 below:

Table 3: Monthly pepper's price in Cambodian local markets (Cambodian Riels:CR)

Months	Monthly pepper's price in Cambodian local markets (Price in CR)			
	2017-GI	2017-Ordinary	2018-GI	2028-Ordinary
Jan	39,000	24,000	40,000	24,000
Feb	40,000	24,000	40,000	24,000
Mar	40,000	25,000	40,000	25,000
Apr	40,000	25,000	40,000	24,000
May	40,000	25,000	40,000	24,000
Jun	40,000	24,000	40,000	24,000
Jul	40,000	24,000	40,000	24,000
Aug	40,000	24,000	40,000	24,000
Sep	40,000	24,000	40,000	24,000
Oct	40,000	24,000		
Nov	40,000	24,000		
Dec	40,000	24,000		

Source: MoC-Daily price bulletin of common goods, 1USD=4,000 Cambodian Riels (CR)

Labour turnover of pepper with GI or CF status

Based on the study show that pepper growers with Geographical Indication (GI) status gets high price compared with Non-GI status. Moreover, growers' return on labour is a few times more than growers without GI status. See the table below:

Table 4. The income of Kampot pepper growers without GI

Pepper types	Proportion by types (%)	Quantity (Kg)	Unit Price (USD/Kg)	Growers' total turnover (USD)
Black pepper	95	19,000	3	57,000
Red pepper	2.5	500	3	1500
White pepper	2.5	500	6	3000
Total		20,000		61,500

Source: (CIRD 2015b)

Table 5. The income of Kampot pepper growers with GI status

Pepper types	Proportion by types (%)	Quantity (Kg)	Unit Price (USD/Kg)	Growers' total turnover (USD)
Black pepper	70	42,000	15	630,000
Red pepper	25	15,000	25	375,000
White pepper	5	3,000	26	78,000
Total		60,000		1,083,000

Source: (CIRD 2015b)

+ For contract farming (CF), the pepper growers with contract farming get more turnovers (profit) than pepper growers without contract farming around five times for mean per household and two times for mean per hectare. See the table below:

Inputs and Income	Household Mean		Mean per Hectare	
	Contract Farmers (CF)	Non-CF	Contract Farmers (CF)	Non-CF
Material Inputs (\$)	1,776.81	1,862.43	2,331.65	6,470.42
Labor Inputs (\$)	265.54	118.26	348.46	410.87
Production Inputs (\$)	2,042.35	1,980.70	2,680.11	6,881.29
Net Income (\$)	14,643.64	4,443.83	19,216.35	15,438.64
Profits (\$)	12,601.29	2,463.13	16,536.24	8,557.35

Figure 10. The turnover (profit) of pepper production between CF and Non-CF in 2014. Source: Journal of Mekong Societies, 2016 (Thong & Chao 2016)

Flow of information

For Tboung Khmum Pepper growers, the information flow is not transparent across the value chain. Both Cambodian collectors and Vietnamese collectors control the market information in their regions. In addition, the main collectors have their own specific distribution channels, this can give them more market power to control price (price maker) at the farm gate. However, for export companies (registered exporters) need to find buyers in the importing countries first then make contracts with main collectors or traders. After that, the companies try to collect peppers from main collectors or traders in the requirement volumes by focusing on standard and quality. Based on study reviews, growers access to market information comes from two sources. First, Cambodian local collectors and Vietnamese collectors who could manipulate price anytime. Second, growers want to get money immediately after harvesting since they need to pay operational costs that they borrowed from Micro-Finance Institutes (MFIs) or private creditors. Hence, they do not have power to bargain prices with collectors or traders (price taker). This situation, it means that collectors put pressure on growers to sell their pepper shortly after harvest by just doing basic drying with sundry and never doing value adding on their produce.

For Kampot Pepper growers, the information flow is far better than their counterpart (Tboung Khmum). Since most of pepper growers in Kampot Province belong to Kampot Pepper Agricultural Cooperative (KAMPACO). This cooperative plays a crucial role to share market information to members. Moreover, it also shares agricultural techniques of pepper planting, harvesting, and grading among the members. In addition, Kampot Pepper Promotion Association (KPPA) helps KAMPACO members to know the requirements of buyers and buying volume of the companies. Furthermore, Kampot Pepper got the GI status from the Ministry of Commerce of Cambodia and European Unions (EU) in 2010 (Thorng & Chao 2016). Hence, growers of Kampot Pepper get unfair-advantaged in term of market prices, product quality, production techniques, and production volumes compared with Tboung Khmum and other provinces growers. Kampot Pepper growers are price makers.

SWOT analysis

SWOT analysis is tool to analyse sector internal and external forces. SWOT stands for strength, weakness, opportunity, and threat. Strengths and weaknesses are the internal forces of the sector. It can be reputation, certificate, location, product quality, brand, and so on. Opportunities and threats are external force of the sector. It refers to competitors, prices, natural disaster, diseases, and regulations. They are outside of the sector. The industry can use SWOT analysis at any time to assess the performance of the sector or specific product. Here is the SWOT analysis of pepper product in Cambodia.

Table 6. SWOT analysis of pepper in Cambodia

Challenges

Based on the finding of the above challenges, the study identifies the overall challenges that the pepper industry in Cambodia faces. Here are some challenges that the pepper industry in Cambodia often face:

-Limited pepper planted areas, post-harvest, and processing techniques among growers make them in high risk particularly smallholder growers. It is more challenging when they face with pests and diseases. Consequently, they lose their investment or low yield that lead them to lose money. Good agricultural practices (GAP), innovation of planting, post-harvest, and processing techniques are not promoted widely and disseminated to growers.

-Lack of understanding on end user markets requirements since growers are used to sell its produce to local and Vietnamese collectors without drying, cleaning, and grading especially Tboung Khmum pepper growers. Consequently, Tboung Khmum and other provinces pepper could only gain markets in Vietnam and Thailand through the two collectors (local and Vietnam collectors). However, Kampot pepper can export to end user markets such as Japan, Korea, Singapore, U.S, and EU.

-Dependency of neighbouring markets: the markets of Tboung Khmum pepper depend too much on informal export to Vietnam and Thailand. There is a few exporter companies (SELA PEPPER, AMRU, Long Best, Khy Thay, Angkor Green, Thang Huy Phen) tried to export the pepper to end user markets. However it is the opposite for Kampot pepper that most of its exports to end user markets but it is still a small volume of export (30 MT in 2014).

-High interest rate of loans (2%-3% per month) for pepper growers compared with neighbouring countries. Therefore, it is hard for growers to access fund to buy input supplies and want to expand the planted areas particularly smallholder growers.

-Fraudulent use of the name of Kampot pepper. As Kampot pepper is a GI product in the country and EU markets, hence there are many illegal products selling under the name of Kampot pepper. For example, in 2014, it was reported that 200 MT of Kampot pepper were imported by EU countries while the KPPA recorded only 30 MT were exported (Thorng & Chao 2016).

Recommendations

The pepper industry plays a crucial role in Cambodia's agriculture sector, and the development of this industry is important to promote poverty reduction, improve livelihoods, and economic development as a whole. Even though it has been significantly increase in total pepper production over the past two decades, the challenging of market access, product quality, and brand awareness are still a major concern for local growers, traders, processors and exporter companies. To deal with these constraints, there are some solutions as follow:

A. Expand planted areas and productivity:

Pepper growers particularly smallholders can increase their pepper yield if they apply good agricultural practices and innovative techniques by selecting good pepper stem varieties, using quality inputs (fertilizers, natural pesticides or chemicals), and try to care take of pepper plant including weeding, watering, and controlling diseases. To extend their planted areas, smallholder growers can use some of incomes from pepper production and loans from MFIs and banks. There are many MFIs and banks are available for pepper growers. Another way, they can access funds through their cooperatives and associations by requesting to Rural Development Bank to get loans with low interest rate.

B. Improve pepper quality:

Pepper quality can be improved by the planting techniques, which are mentioned above or can be improved by post-harvest activities such as drying techniques, cleaning, and grading. The high quality of peppercorns, the higher price they would get from pepper collectors or exporters. Other potential pepper quality standard for exporting is organic pepper or free chemical pepper. There are more and more end user markets in

developed countries paying attention to organic pepper. Hence, it is a good opportunity for pepper growers to improve quality for target markets by implementing good agricultural practice (GAP).

C. Focus on end user exporting markets

Most of Cambodian's exporting pepper went to Vietnam and Thailand markets through pepper collectors who informally export. Hence, direct and formal export to end user markets should be focused on. The exporting of Kampot pepper to high value markets (EU) as a model for other provinces to follow up. To get competitive advantages of exporting to end user markets, it is crucial to know their demand of pepper, premium quality, and better cost position.

D. Pay attention on contract farming (CF) and organic status

Based on literature views show that CF of pepper can improve the income of grower households around five times compared with non-contract farming (Thorng & Chao 2016). Moreover, CF is regarded as a mechanism for poverty reduction and improvement for smallholder producers (World Bank 2008). Organic or free chemical pepper has been considered by consumers in the developed countries markets. Hence, it is a good market opportunity for pepper growers in Cambodia to pay attention on this niche market. The more diversified products, the better options for finding markets of pepper growers.

E. Do brand awareness

Kampot pepper gets competitive advantage compared with its counterparts (Tboung Khmum and other peppers).

Since Kampot pepper has been selected as number one best pepper in the globe by chefs and foodies for more than a century (Farmlink, 2018). Moreover, it has a certificate of Protected Geographical Indication (PGI) from the Ministry of Commerce (MoC) and EU countries in 2009 and 2010 respectively. However, Tboung Khmum pepper can request GI certificate also or try to promote its brand as trade mark to compete with Kampot pepper or other countries' pepper. Brand equity is a core value of products to sell in the markets. That why most of the companies try to do promotions to advertise their products or services. Here are some suggestions for promotion strategies especially for Tboung Khmum pepper:

-Make product stickers: It is necessary for Tboung Khmum pepper to enhance brand awareness by creating label of own produce since it is the first thing before doing other promotional activities. To do this, they can work with Da Memot cooperative or pepper growers in the province to agree on product label by including name, logo and slogan. The label should be discussed with pepper exporters as they involve heavily of using it too.

-Establish digital marketing: It is necessary to create website and social media such as Facebook, Instagram, WeChat, YouTube, WhatsApp, and so on. Then, it should upload video spot ads of Cambodian pepper and

always update information on the website and social media page. This digital marketing is a tool to disseminate information to growers and buyers. For growers, it can share about planting techniques; pepper processing, market information, events, and requirement of pepper quality from buyers. For buyers or consumers, it can broadcast about pepper prices, type of peppers, recipes, produce advantages, quantity of production, and sale promotion.

-Trade show: To raise awareness of pepper brand, it is important to have national or international trade exhibition and cooking shows to the public. The brand image of pepper will be recognized effectively within these events. For example, the annual trade show of the Ministry of Commerce in Cambodia (one province, one product) and China-Asean trade exhibition, which often celebrate in China and Asean countries.

-Special events: There are several special events in the country to show peppers to audiences such as Ploughing Day, Angkor Sangkran, Sea festival, River festival, and other exhibition conducted by private companies and other organizations.

-Super markets shelves (for local consumption): There are more and more supermarkets (Eaon 1, Eaon 2, Lucky, Macro, Bayon, Sorya, Sovanna, Rathana Plaza, Chip Mong, marts, and so on) opened in Cambodia. Hence, it is an opportunities to contact those retailers to put pepper products on their shelves.

-Online shopping (focus on international markets): Many people nowadays are using electronic devices such as smart phones, tablets, and computers to buy products online. Hence, Cambodian pepper products can sell online in those retailer websites such as nhom24, foodpenda, Alibaba, Amazon, Ebay, Taobao, Tianmao, and so on.

Conclusion

An analysis of value chain plays a crucial role to analyse all the factors and actors that affect the chain of pepper production. Based on the analysis, the study found that pepper diversifications (black, white, red, green, ground, oil, oleoresin, and medicines), premium quality, and information flow can make the produce more value adding with the demand growth potential in the end user markets. Moreover, the improvement of delivery system can facilitate the transportation of the produces to become market oriented and reduce inventory. Moreover, CF, GI, and organic status are essential for PVC (pepper value chains) actors namely input suppliers, growers, collectors, processors, cooperatives and associations, and exporter companies to push the produce for exporting to end user markets. Furthermore, the government tries to improve infrastructure and commit to strictly control licence of GI, organic certificates, and also combat counterfeit/fraud produces to make sure everything is qualified based on the criteria of those licenses since Cambodia has a good image of GI and organic status from local and international markets (EU markets). Last but not least, technology upgrading is also a key to develop the industry especially planting techniques, processing, and packaging. The study found that it is potential for investments particularly in processing and exporting since the government

priority investments by providing tax break for investors from three to five years and tax exception for importing agricultural machineries.

Therefore, to make Cambodian pepper for high value markets and potential for local consumption, it needs: 1). shorten the chains by eliminating Vietnamese collectors and reducing local collectors through direct buying from processors or exporter companies, 2). combat informal trading to neighbouring countries (Vietnam & Thailand) by setting up factories to process the peppercorns, 3). diversify produces (not just peppercorn but can be other forms of pepper) , 4). enhance delivery system by improving of roads, railways, and seaports, 5). set up premium quality of pepper by adopting agricultural technologies and GAP (good agricultural practices), 6). build brand equity through exhibition campaigns both local and international markets, and 7). collaborate of all actors in PVC to work closely together.

References

- Anna, Him. *Description of Kampot pepper production* . Kampot : Kampot Pepper Promotion Association (KPPA), 2014.
- CIRD. *Memot Pepper Market System Analysis* . Phnom Penh : Cambodian Institute for Reserach and Rural Development(CIRD), 2015.
- Edgar. *Reaping what you sow*. Phnom Penh : Phnom Penh Post, 2016.
- Farmlink. *Farm Link Company*. n.d. <https://www.farmlink-cambodia.com/> (accessed Sep 25, 2018).
- IPC. "Interanational Pepper Community ." 01 01 2018. <http://www.ipcnet.org/ipc/?p=d&id=7&start=7> (accessed 04 30, 2018).
- Kong SIM, Kimlong Heng. *Memot Pepper Market System Analysis*. Phnom Penh: Cambodian Institute for Research and Rural Development (CIRD), 2015.
- Lak, Youssef. "Value chain analysis of Memot pepper in Cambodia." *Australian Agribusiness Perspective* 21, no. 2 (2018): 24-42.
- Naveen Kumar, H.S. "Value Chain Analysis of Black Pepper in Karnataka." 01 July 2013. <http://krishikosh.egranth.ac.in/handle/1/83298> (accessed 03 10, 2018).
- NEDSPICE. *NEDSPICE* . 2017. http://www.nedspice.com/upload/docs/170601_Nedspice_-_ESA_Pepper_Crop_Report_vFinal.pdf (accessed 04 29, 2018).
- Prak. "Pepper Value Chain Analysis." Phnom Penh: Cambodian Institute for Research and Rural Development (CIRD), 2015.
- Ra Thorng, Sinh Chao. "Contract Farming Arrangements in Cambodia:The Case of Kampot Pepper (Piper nigrum)." *Journal of Mekong Societies*, 2016: 45-69.
- Selapepper. *Sela Pepper Company*. n.d. <https://selapepper.com/#top> (accessed Sep 12, 2018).
- Yogesh, M.S and Dr. S. Mokshapathy . "Production and Export Performance of Black Pepper ." *International Journal of Hummanities and Social Science Invention* 2, no. 4 (2013): 36-44.

Authors name and details: Mr. Pisith SOK
M.S in Agri-business at Adelaide University, South Australia (SA).

Deputy Director, Planning and Cooperation Department, Ministry of Labour and Vocational Training (MLVT), Royal Government of Cambodia (RGC)

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